

Global Readiness for AI-Integrated Education: Students' Competence and Perceptions of Generative AI in Learning and Assessment

Narayan Sapkota^{1*}, Basanta Prasad Adhikari², Vikas Kumar Khare³, Sabina Adhikari⁴, Abina Bishwokarma⁴

¹Department of Management, ISMT College, Bharatpur, Nepal

²Head of Research Committee, Oxford College of Engineering and Management, Gairidhar, Nepal

³Assistant Professor, SOM- ITM University Gwalior, India

⁴Research Assistant, Oxford College of Engineering and Management, Gairidhar, Nepal

*Corresponding email: sapkota.narayan1986@gmail.com

*ORCID: 0009-0000-7438-8552

Abstract

This study is about global readiness for AI-integrated education: students' competence and perceptions of generative AI in learning and assessment in higher education in Nepal and Indonesia. The purpose of this study was to understand the perceptions and experiences of higher level teachers about the roles of Generative AI in classroom learning and assessment in higher education. We applied qualitative approach along with interview method to collect data from nine teachers in Nepal and Indonesia. Semi-structured interview questions were used as research instrument to collect data. Content analysis was used to analyse the interview data based on inductive approach which included preparation of data from recorded audio to texts, selecting key codes and converting key codes into subcategories. The subcategories were converted into main categories. Ethical criteria was followed during the research processes focusing on interviewees' security, anonymity, and consent of participation in this research. The interviewees highlight that a fair picture of how higher level educational institutions can use AI in classroom teaching. They not only highlight how technology can help students learn and teachers teach, but they also highlight some of the major problems and risks that higher level educational institutions face. They summarised that the best thing is that they get better at what they do and learn more. Teachers often use AI to make lesson plans because it is quick and easy to find accurate, helpful, and up-to-date information, which makes the materials better and saves time.

Keywords: *AI-integrated education, classroom learning, generative AI, global readiness, higher education, students' competence skills*